

World Heritage Historic Construction as Narratives of Climate Change: From Historical to Structural Analyses

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Abstract. This paper presents preliminary investigations of two world heritage structures: Durham Castle in the UK and the dome of San Giorgio Church in Ragusa, Italy. These sites have been identified as pilot sites within the ongoing project “WRENCH – Whispers of Time: Heritage as Narratives of Climate Change”, funded by the Belmont Forum. The WRENCH project aims to evaluate the relationship between climate change, heritage, and local communities, using narratives to raise awareness of how climate change can affect the perception and use of heritage sites. The paper describes the initial steps critical to developing the knowledge phase. In particular, the historical analysis aimed at investigating the construction phases, modifications of the structural layout and use over the centuries, and the effects of past events on both the sites and the communities are described. This then served as the basis for digital surveys performed using laser scanners and UAV-based photogrammetry, experimental in-situ dynamic identification of the structures and preliminary identification of material characteristics through in-situ non-destructive tests. Furthermore, the paper shows the potential offered by the structural analysis approach not only in predicting the response of historic structures subjected to climate change but also in informing visual products fundamental to WRENCH's targets.

Keywords: Historic Masonry Structures, Digital Surveys, Non-destructive Tests, Numerical Models, Structural Analyses, Trans-disciplinarity

1 | Introduction

Extreme weather events and environmental disasters, such as floods, droughts, fires, and other threats, are affecting various communities around the world due to a clear shift in climate patterns. The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change [1] confirms that climate change is one of the most pressing issues for humans, more-than-humans, and their living environments, including the legacy of the past and the heritage systems that characterize each local community.

Climate change, alongside other burdens, is one of the main causes of heritage loss [2], affecting both so-called “natural heritage” [3] and “cultural heritage” [4]. However, heritage itself can no longer be easily categorized as either natural versus cultural or tangible versus intangible. Concepts such as territorial heritage [5] and living heritage [6] acknowledge the intertwined relations that characterize heritage as a multifaceted system that is constantly made, unmade, negotiated, and recreated [7]. Moreover, climate change is one of the major threats not only to built environments but, more importantly, to some of the most vulnerable classes and populations around the globe, who are forced into a path of migration as climate refugees [8], carrying “heritage” with them as a system of memories, knowledge, abilities, and perceptions [9]. The impact of climate change on heritage is thus one of the complex issues of the current times that cannot be addressed with reductionist and simplistic approaches to science [10] but requires the ability to think creatively to advance knowledge and technical know-how in a transdisciplinary manner [11].

With these premises, the project “WRENCH – Whispers of Time: Heritage as Narratives of Climate Change”, funded by the Belmont Forum – an international partnership that mobilizes funding for supporting research concerned on global environmental issues – aims to experiment with the challenge of trans-disciplinarity in addressing the nexus between climate change and an expanded concept of heritage. This concept incorporates not only buildings, monuments, and UNESCO sites but also the complex systems of relations and processes that constantly redefine heritage as it is perceived, used, and cared for, by the people living with it. After a paragraph introducing the theoretical and methodological framework for the WRENCH project

(Section 2), the authors present the pilot sites at the core of this article (Section 3): Durham Castle, UK, and the dome of San Giorgio Church in Ragusa, Italy.

The descriptions of these sites derive from the WRENCH transdisciplinary methodological approach, which arises from the intersection of various disciplinary backgrounds, spanning engineering to the humanities, and includes the involvement of non-academic partners in the writing process. Finally, Section 4 highlights some concluding remarks and open challenges for the next steps of the project.

2 | The WRENCH project

WRENCH envisions heritage as an ensemble of legacies and the narratives connected to them, considering storytelling – in the form of words, arts, and more experimental practices – as integral to the heritage system, just like a church or a monument. For this reason, the project's methodological approach is based on a transformative blend of disciplines – as in the transdisciplinary approach – looking at heritage from a variety of perspectives. Environmental scientists, civil/structural engineers, urban planners, anthropologists, historians, archaeologists, and museologists are intersecting their backgrounds, questions, lenses, methods, and skills not only among themselves but also through the involvement of local communities. As such, the transdisciplinary effort is pursued as a blend of forms of knowledge and practices, both within and beyond academic walls, through the direct engagement of at least one non-academic partner on each pilot site, which acts as a catalyst for the process of community engagement. WRENCH's transdisciplinary methodology is grounded in the following pillars: i) Applying advanced generations of climate models to carry out data analysis related to climate change; ii) Investigating the effects of extreme environmental conditions on historical materials and structures through in-situ physical testing and numerical simulations; iii) Assessing the impact of the nexus between climate change and heritage as perceived by the people living in the pilot sites through historical research, storytelling, and tools derived from social museology. This assessment will also envision future transformations using methods from community-based planning. More broadly, the project will incorporate tools from the field of environmental humanities. As such, WRENCH develops a holistic framework for assessing the nexus between climate change and heritage and envisioning strategies for the care of heritage in its multifaceted dimensions. It also encourages the development of a larger network of researchers, stakeholders, associations, and residents through the launch and maintenance of the Living Heritage Platform, which will be hosted on the project's website and envisioned as an interactive tool aimed at connecting actors and sites at the transnational level.

This article is focused on two world heritage sites as case studies: Durham Castle in the UK and the San Giorgio Church in Ragusa, Italy. The project activities will include laboratory tests of historic materials under various environmental conditions, environmental and structural monitoring, and climatic and structural analyses to predict the long-term effects of climate change on historic structures. In the next steps of the project, they will also blend with another set of activities developed in the broader framework of the environmental humanities. This study presents the results of preliminary steps, which are propaedeutic to proper structural analyses. These activities consist of surveys performed on the two pilot cases using drones and laser scanners, as well as initial in-situ material tests and dynamic identification.

3 | The Pilot Sites

WRENCH will conduct research in six pilot sites across northern and southern contexts, from the UK to southern Italy, Spain, and Argentina. Each site has been identified for the specific nuance it adds to the project. Specifically, the two sites that are at the core of this article – the Durham Castle in the UK and the San Giorgio Church in Ragusa, southern Italy – provide examples of how monumental heritage is entangled with material dynamics and ephemeral legacies that unveil its multifaceted character and the ways in which this is threatened by climate change. The other cases – namely, a former military hospital in Naples and a bell tower in Civitavecchia, also in southern Italy, along with “Montes de Galicia” in Spain and the Matanza-Riachuelo River in Argentina – will complement the research by adding layers to the understanding of heritage as a living and evolving system of relations.

3.1 Durham Castle

Durham Castle, positioned at the north end of medieval Palace Green adjacent to Durham Cathedral, is a building of outstanding international importance. Durham Castle along with Durham Cathedral were designated as a UNESCO World Heritage site in 1986 and are among the greatest monuments to the Norman Conquest of Britain. As stated by the UNESCO, the Castle and Cathedral have remained in use for almost 1000 years: the Cathedral as a religious building, educational centre, and place of pilgrimage; and the Castle, first as the home of the Prince Bishops, and then as the home of Durham University, established in 1832 – the third oldest university in England. Construction of the Castle, which follows the usual motte and bailey design favoured by the Normans, began in 1072 under the orders of William the Conqueror, six years after the Norman conquest of England. During the first years of William's reign, the new king struggled to maintain control of northern England, experiencing rebellion from the local population, raids from Scotland and threats of invasion from overseas. Durham Castle was therefore constructed as a military fortress, which then evolved into a palace for the Prince Bishops of Durham, commissioned by William to represent his authority in the north. Over the centuries the castle has fulfilled various uses such as a makeshift hospital for wounded Scottish soldiers during the English Civil Wars and as a training site for RAF officers in World War II. The University began to occupy the castle in 1837 when it became the home of University College, the oldest college of Durham University. The quality of the buildings within the castle compound that have survived since Norman times is outstanding. They include a chapel space built around 1080 and known to be the oldest standing building in Durham, an undercroft to the original west great hall, a complete north range with gallery and an intricately carved mid-12th century archway. Bishop Tunstall was responsible for the addition of a new chapel and a two-storey gallery in the mid-16th century, and Bishop Cosin added the Black Stairs after the Restoration of the Monarchy in 1660. In 1952 Castle was Grade I listed and today it is home to around 100 students, with more college members living offsite. The castle still houses the college kitchen, dining rooms, common rooms, chapels, library and bar. Durham Castle is open to the public by guided tour and welcomes in the region of 30,000 visitors a year. Many social and official functions of the university are held in the Great Hall and State Rooms, and during vacations the site takes on more roles as a conference centre and hotel. The castle is a challenging site to look after due to its age and complexity and is suffering from accumulated structural issues. Externally, parapet stones are failing, ashlar work is eroded, window units are splitting, and joints are devoid of mortar. The buildings have been modified so many times that they are not fully understood, and any restoration or repairing/retrofitting work requires careful preparation and investigation. Works consistently reveal previously unknown issues once begun, highlighting the importance of innovative strategies to cope with the future effects of climate change. As a part of a valuable heritage, the Durham Castle collection has developed organically and reflects the changing use and purpose of Durham Castle. It comprises around 3000 objects relating to the Bishops of Durham, to Durham University and University College. Durham Castle was never a hereditary possession, its management passing instead through the hands of a succession of Bishops. This has affected the nature of the collections, as with each change in Bishop the possessions of the previous incumbent were generally removed. Nevertheless, some later bishops (in particular Bishops Cosin and Crewe) left material in Durham Castle. After the transfer of Durham Castle to University College, Bishop Maltby further added to the collections left by the preceding Bishops of Durham. From 1837 the collections developed in new ways as a reflection of the evolving role of University College within the University. The stability of the internal spaces, where the collections are stored and displayed, is directly connected to the stability of the external fabric of the castle and therefore the collections' safety depends on our forward-looking monitoring of external deterioration.

3.2 Survey of the Castle

A 3D digital exterior survey of the entire monumental complex of Durham Castle was conducted as part of an ongoing 3D scanning project of the Castle [12] The exterior was surveyed using a DJI Mini 2 UAS, which has a 1/2.3-inch camera sensor with a resolution of 12MP. The survey was conducted over a period of two days, with the keep and the inner walls of the courtyard scanned on the first day. On the second day, the exterior walls and the western side around the Great Hall were captured. Use of a terrestrial laser scanner or handheld cameras was also considered but would have been impractical due to accessibility limitations on the steep hillside. The preliminary results from this ongoing 3D drone survey of Durham Castle are shown in Fig. 1, where a birds-eye perspective (Fig. 1a) and a view of the riverside part of the Castle (Fig. 1b) of the 3D model are rendered. There were various constraints that limited what could be captured, resulting in the affected areas having a lower Ground Sample Distance (GSD). As the Castle is used for student

accommodation, drone flights near windows of bedrooms were prohibited due to privacy and Health and Safety concerns (which also prohibited the use of a heavier Mavic drone on this site). The site morphology and presence of vegetation further limited drone operability, as any hypothetical optimal flights path were blocked by trees, with some of their branches nearly touching the buildings. Particularly for surveying the part overhanging the River Wear (Figure 1b), the drone had to be flown over four times as high to avoid crashing into trees, quartering the GSD and lowering accuracy in this part of the model. This, combined with United Kingdom drone laws, a nearby no-fly zone, insurance regulations, terrible British weather, and the complex and irregular shape of the Castle, added to the challenging nature of this 3D survey. These issues required complicated and irregular flight paths, so relying on a grid pattern was not viable. In order to capture as much of the site as possible, the drone was flown fully manually, allowing us to dodge or even fly into small gaps between the trees. Furthermore, great care had to be taken to ensure consistent overlap. In total, 1,934 aerial photographs were taken and processed into a 3D model using photogrammetry, using the software Agisoft Metashape Pro v1.7.2 [13], resulting in a mesh consisting of 287 million polygons, with highly detailed textures and colour data achieved for the parts that were not blocked by trees.

Fig. 1a: Digital model of the Castle: (Bird-eye perspective)

Fig. 1b. Digital model of the Castle: riverside part.

From Figs. 1a,1b, it can be observed that the Castle, which can be classified as an aggregate of buildings rather than a single building, is characterised by a high structural irregularity. This structural variety is also reflected in a high material heterogeneity. As an example of material heterogeneity, Fig. 2 shows some views of the walls of the northeast portion of the Castle at the internal court (Figs. 2a, 2b), showing a better state of conservation, in contrast with the more evident structural damage involving the external walls of the same part of the construction (Fig. 2c). These differences make it clear that there is a need for systematic mapping and characterization of the various materials propaedeutic to the numerical modelling of the Castle. The detailed 3D digital survey allows for mapping the degradation mechanisms involving the external faces of masonry walls and monitoring their evolution (through periodic surveys and systematic

comparisons of the 3D models). An example of a deterioration mechanism is the alveolar erosion of Durham Sandstone, leading to the gradual loss of material (as shown in Fig. 3 [14]), requiring the replacement of deteriorated stones with new ones. Understanding the role of climate change in accelerating this process will be the object of the following research tasks

Fig. 2a. Different masonry bonds and state of conservation revealed by the survey: top

Fig. 2b. Different masonry bonds and state of conservation revealed by the survey:
bottom level of the internal court wall

Fig. 2c. Different masonry bonds and state of conservation revealed by the survey:
external wall of the northern building.

Fig. 3. Example of a) mild, b) moderate, and c) severe alveolar erosion (from [14]).

3.3 San Giorgio Church

Two devastating earthquakes struck the southeast side of the Sicilian Island (Italy) in January 1693. During these events, 49 towns reported damages, with an estimated number of 60,000 to 90,000 fatalities. After the earthquakes, the entire Noto Valley became a stage for rebirth under a new urban planning vision, leading to the emergence of the well-known Sicilian late Baroque architectural style, included in the UNESCO World Heritage list since 2002. Ragusa Ibla, one of the main towns in that area, was destroyed during the earthquakes, necessitating the rebuilding and eventual relocation of the main Church. The final decision regarding the reconstruction took nearly fifty years, and in 1738, the famous Sicilian architect Rosario Gagliardi was appointed as the designer for the new San Giorgio Church (Fig. 4). It is a Latin-cross-shaped church, divided into three naves by a series of ten columns with circular arches on top. The bases of the columns are made of black “pece” stone. In Sicily, bitumen-impregnated asphalt rock is called “pece” (pitch) and the significant mineral deposits containing this brownish, oily rock, located south of Ragusa on the Iblean plateau, were known since ancient times. The “pece” stone blocks were also used decoratively in other parts of the Church, while local calcareous stone is generally used for the masonry blocks. In front of the Church, a long, monumental staircase connects it to the city square, representing the legacy of the theatrical fashion in late Baroque style that dominated the post-earthquake reconstruction in Eastern Sicily. The original drawings are dated 1744 (Fig. 5). Before it, a church entitled to San Nicola was present on the same site, which, according to the tradition, was the oldest Church in Ibla.

Fig.4. San Giorgio church: (a) view from the square, and (b) the XIX-century dome.

The dome (Fig.4b), as in most churches built in oriental Sicily after the earthquake, was originally designed lower than the façade and with thick walls. In contrast to this design, the construction of the dome started in 1820, 127 years after the earthquake and after the death of Gagliardi, when it was drastically redesigned by the foreman Carmelo Cultraro. According to the new design, the dome is set on a circular ring located about 20 m from the ground level and supported by four pendentives that depart from the central arches of the Latin Cross of the Church. Structurally, it can be distinguished into the following main elements: the drum, made up of 16 pairs of columns arranged radially with plinths at the base resting on a circular base, with an estimated height of 5.84 m and diameters of 70 cm (external columns) and 60 cm (internal columns); the ring, made of soft limestone blocks with a height of 3.76 m; the dome, having an internal radius of 5.34 m and a height of 5.12 m; the lantern, made by thin and slender columns. San Giorgio church is nowadays one of the most iconic results of the rebuilding period that constellated the valley of Noto with new churches and buildings.

Fig. 5. Original drawing of San Giorgio church, kindly granted by the San Giorgio Museum.

3.4 Survey of the Church

An architectural and structural survey programme was carried out on the entire church. The morphological and topographical characteristics of the built heritage significantly influenced the methodological and operational choices of the survey campaign, which took place over four days. The elevated position of the Church, the limited access due to the staircases and perimeter gate, the restricted space around the structure, and adverse weather conditions required careful planning of the operations. In particular, the poor lighting of the interiors necessitated the optimization of acquisition parameters, as well as making the most of the available natural light. Data acquisition was carried out using an integrated approach that included range-based techniques through terrestrial laser scanning (Fig. 6) and image-based techniques through terrestrial and aerial photographic acquisitions (Fig. 7).

Fig. 6. Survey Activities: Laser Scanner and UAS

The range-based three-dimensional survey was conducted using a Topcon GLS-2200 laser scanner, characterized by high metric accuracy and the integration of topographic principles, thanks to a liquid biaxial compensator with a compensation range of $\pm 6'$. The acquisition began from the external forecourt, continuing inside the Church, documenting the central nave, side naves, apse, service areas, and the elevated choir. Subsequently, the survey covered the entire external perimeter of the Cathedral, with particular attention to the site's altimetric variations and the transitions between pedestrian pathways and staircases. The closure of the polygon was performed at the corresponding square in front, coinciding with the initial scan, ensuring the robustness of the model and reducing systematic errors. A total of 59 laser scans were recorded, ensuring detailed coverage of the structure.

Fig. 7. Image-Based Processing.

In the last two days of the campaign, it was possible to carry out the image-based survey, albeit intermittently due to adverse weather conditions. The flights were conducted entirely in manual mode, following a double orthogonal grid survey pattern, with an overlap sufficient to ensure the quality of the photogrammetric process. The acquisition, carried out with a DJI Mavic 2 Pro UAS, aimed at documenting the roofs to integrate the geometric data obtained from the laser scanner with high-resolution photogrammetric information. Additionally, for detailed surveying of the church portal, close-up acquisitions were made using a GoPro Hero 6, allowing for precise documentation of the material and decorative features of the façade. In total, 1,168 aerial photographic datasets and 2,651 terrestrial photographic datasets were acquired. Data processing was conducted using proprietary software for managing laser scans and commercial software based on photogrammetric algorithms for photogrammetry. The two workflows produced point clouds with different characteristics: the laser scanner yielded a high-density and metric-accurate point cloud, while the photogrammetric survey provided a cloud characterized by greater chromatic richness, which was clearly manifested in the definition of the polygonal model's textures (Fig. 7). The subsequent research phase will focus on integrating these datasets, aiming to accurately evaluate the thickness of the external walls of the church toward developing accurate numerical models to investigate the church structural behaviour. The structural experimental activities were aimed at preliminarily characterising the mechanical behaviour of the Church through non-destructive testing. In particular, the following tests were performed (Fig. 8).

Fig.8. Non-destructive experimental activities on the Church:
(a) AVT, (b) hammer rebound test, (c) sonic test, and (d) GP

Ambient Vibration Tests (AVTs) were aimed at characterising the dynamic features of the façade (frequencies and modal shapes), eventually allowing for some limited consideration on the interaction between it and the nave walls. Six force-balanced, high-sensitivity accelerometers were placed on the façade and one orthogonal wall, and several 20-minute acquisitions at a 200 Hz sampling rate were recorded for two days. Hammer rebound tests on stone units allowed for preliminary characterisation of the stones used in the church construction. Three stone types were identified, including Ragusa black stone, which has higher mechanical characteristics, and two calcareous stones with slightly different superficial hardness. Sonic tests on columns record the flight time of the elastic wave generated by an instrumented hammer to arrive at a receiving sensor; they allow for a characterisation of the wave velocity inside the masonry. By performing several measurements around the column, it was possible to identify an external layer, made of good-quality stone, and an internal core of lower mechanical characteristics. Ground Penetrating Radar (GPR) was carried out on columns and walls to identify the internal morphology of masonry, including homogeneity, voids, and irregularities.

4 | Concluding remarks

For Durham Castle, despite the challenges encountered during the survey, this initial phase of exploration already shows promising results. The 3D model highlights many locations of interest that warrant further research and has potential for future non-destructive applications in the study of these buildings. We aim to overcome current limitations posed by site morphology and vegetation by further improving the 3D model through additional drone surveys and merging it with future laser scans and with Virtual Reality models to show the evolution of damage over time.

For the Cathedral of San Giorgio, the architectural survey campaign has enabled the acquisition of a complete and integrated dataset, leveraging the potential offered by digital technologies for the documentation and analysis of built heritage. The methodological approach adopted has allowed us to overcome operational challenges related to the context, significantly contributing to the knowledge and preservation of this historical asset. The results of the survey activities will then be used to create an accurate structural model of the Church, which will be calibrated based on the results of the non-destructive mechanical tests. This will be the starting point for more accurate analyses involving the degradation of materials because of climate change, aimed at estimating the building's capacity over time.

In both cases, the challenge will be to translate the results of these activities into designed visualization outcomes that can be integrated with qualitative data and used in the process related to investigating a variety of perspectives and raising awareness of climate change-related risks. In other words, the challenge is to integrate the engineering perspective with that derived from the field of environmental humanities, as seen in the methodological approach of the WRENCH project. Such transdisciplinary integration aims to construct consistent narratives that can tell the story of the relationship between climate change and heritage sites, including the voices of the people who engage with these sites for various reasons, as they inhabit, work at, and care for the sites. This challenge will pertain not only to the two case studies presented in the article but also to all the pilot cases of the WRENCH project and, more generally, to all heritage sites that can provide insights into the climate change-heritage nexus. How to cite: Pappalardo, Giusy, Andreoni, Samuele, Armiero, Marco, Chisari, Corrado, De Matteis, Gianfranco, Jansen, Alexander C.Q., Iaderosa, Rosina, Iovane, Domenico, Occhipinti, Giuseppe, Osman, Ashraf, Pantò, Bartolomeo, Rennie, Gillian, and Mattia Zizi (forthcoming). "World Heritage Historic Construction as Narratives of Climate Change: From Historical to Structural Analyses", Paper presented at the *14th International Conference on Structural Analysis of Historical Constructions (SAHC)*, Lausanne, 15-17 September 2025.

Acknowledgement

Paper presented within the project WRENCH – Whispers of Time. Heritage as Narratives of Climate Change, funded by the Belmont Forum, UKRI grant AH/Z000076/1, AEI grant PCI2024-153536, <https://webs.uab.cat/wrench>. The authors thank the Curia of Ragusa for the opportunity to feature the San Giorgio Dome as a pilot site in the WRENCH project.

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WRENCH:
PCI2024-153536

Pappalardo, Giusy, Andreoni, Samuele, Armiero, Marco, Chisari, Corrado, De Matteis, Gianfranco, Jansen, Alexander C.Q., Iaderosa, Rosina, Iovane, Domenico, Occhipinti, Giuseppe, Osman, Ashraf, Pantò, Bartolomeo, Rennie, Gillian, and Mattia Zizi (forthcoming). "World Heritage Historic Construction as Narratives of Climate Change: From Historical to Structural Analyses", Paper presented at the 14th International Conference on Structural Analysis of Historical Constructions (SAHC), 15-17 September 2025, Lausanne
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.18621036